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Supplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Abstract

Evidence suggests that lifestyle changes are a crucial aspect in the design of decarbonisation strategies towards the achievement of Paris Agreement's goals. However, most mitigation scenarios developed with Integrated Assessment and Energy System Models often lack a reliable representation of lifestyle changes, therefore modelled pathways overlook the intricate interplay between the impacts of behavioural change and climate policy instruments. This study addresses this critical gap by introducing methodological improvements in leading sectoral energy models (PRIMES-BuiMo, EDGE-Buildings) to simulate more accurately the effect of potential lifestyle transformations in households. The improved models were used to develop scenarios for the residential sector of the European Union up to 2050, considering two different climate targets and three distinct assumptions about the adoption rate and intensity of lifestyle changes. The findings reveal that lifestyle transformations can lead to substantial reductions in energy use and CO₂ emissions of households. Important cost reductions, especially for fuel expenses, resulting from lifestyle changes could help mitigate the risk of energy poverty for vulnerable households in the decarbonisation context. A decomposition analysis of energy savings by behavioural measure showcases the benefit to incorporate lifestyle changes with high mitigation potential such as thermostat set-point adjustments and dwellings downsizing in ambitious climate targets. Showcasing the pivotal role of lifestyle changes in achieving low-carbon futures signals the need for policy to address the drivers and key barriers of demand-side transitions.

1. Introduction

The Paris Agreement (PA) (UNFCCC 2016) has set ambitious targets for countries to collectively limit the rise in average global temperature to well below 2 °C, and pursue 1.5 °C, above pre-industrial levels, in an effort to avert the adverse effects of climate change. At the same time, global pathways modelled with Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) signify that drastic reductions in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are required across economic sectors to fulfill the PA's goals (Rogelj *et al* 2018, IPCC 2023). In particular, the IPCC AR6 highlights the important role lifestyle changes and demand-side transitions can play in the decarbonisation of end-use sectors, including buildings and transport (Creutzig *et al* 2022b). Demand-side transitions can also support the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and improve human well-being, through for example their positive effect on health and air quality (IEA 2021, Creutzig *et al* 2022a).

Buildings could have a major contribution towards system-wide decarbonisation in a 1.5 °C world (Wang *et al* 2018, Cabeza *et al* 2022, Camarasa *et al* 2022). This could be delivered through GHG savings achieved based

on energy efficiency advancements, electrification and the increased penetration of renewables, and sufficiency measures, including lifestyle changes. For the latter, research has shown that occupant behaviour is an important determinant of actual energy use in buildings (Yun and Steemers 2011, Delzendeh *et al* 2017) and therefore behavioural changes may have a considerable GHG mitigation potential (Levesque *et al* 2019, Ivanova *et al* 2020, van den Berg *et al* 2024).

Despite the potential contribution of future lifestyles in net-zero transitions, IAMs and Energy System Models (ESMs)—the computational tools typically used to investigate climate policy - focus more on technological supply-side solutions, while ignoring to a large extent the social aspects of energy transition (Creutzig *et al* 2018, Mathias *et al* 2020, Krumm *et al* 2022). The reasons behind this overlook are (a) the inherent complexity with integrating complex social phenomena in quantitative modelling frameworks constrained to mainly represent technology-led transitions (van den Berg *et al* 2019, Keppo *et al* 2021), (b) the unavailability of data on heterogeneous energy preferences and behaviours (Saujot *et al* 2021) and (c) computational resource constraints (Wiese *et al* 2018). Furthermore, Mastrucci *et al* (2023) argue that socio-behavioural interventions, such as lifestyle changes and social energy-saving practices, which support low energy demand transitions in the buildings sector are often represented partially and through exogenous assumptions in sectoral modelling tools.

Building on previous research (van Sluisveld *et al* 2016, Levesque *et al* 2019, Andreou *et al* 2022, Gaur *et al* 2022, van den Berg *et al* 2024), this paper aims to move the literature forward by comprehensively examining the impact of lifestyle changes on European Union's (EU's) residential buildings sector under different climate policy contexts. This will be achieved through developing scenarios and enhancing sectoral energy models to better represent the drivers and impacts of behavioural changes. Quantification of lifestyle change impacts is based on the output of two modelling tools, namely PRIMES and EDGE-REMIND.

This study's innovation first lies in the development and presentation of scenarios combining multiple ambition levels for climate policy and lifestyle changes in the future. This is an extension of the work done by van Sluisveld *et al* (2016), Grubler *et al* (2018) and Bauer and Sterner (2025) which model a range of climate policy scenarios combined with a single lifestyle change variant, or the work by van den Berg *et al* (2024) which incorporates lifestyle transitions in a single climate policy pathway. The examination of the interactions between the impact of lifestyle changes and climate policies on policy-relevant indicators allows this research to contribute to the emerging discourse to target behavioural shifts as part of effective climate mitigation strategies. Moreover, the modelling enhancements provide a more comprehensive representation of the effect of potential behavioural responses on energy demand for a set of residential end-uses. Lastly, comparison of results concerning key policy indicators between two well-established energy-system models aids in capturing the uncertainty governing the quantification of lifestyle changes and their impacts in the residential sector.

2. Methodology

The study focuses on the evolution of the residential buildings sector of EU-27 countries and the United Kingdom (UK). The analysis is carried out for six scenarios combining two ambition levels of climate policy with three tiers of assumptions about the future adoption rate and intensity of lifestyle changes in the residential sector. Lifestyle modules enhanced to better represent behavioural shifts in the residential domain are integrated in sectoral energy models. This allows for a comprehensive analysis of the effects of changing consumer behaviours on several policy indicators including final energy use, CO₂ emissions and system costs.

The sectoral energy models utilised in this study are PRIMES-BuiMo and EDGE-Buildings, which is interlinked with the REMIND-Buildings integrated-assessment model. These models have been previously employed to support policy impact assessments (EC 2018), shape energy transition outlook scenarios (Capros *et al* 2021) and study energy-system transformations towards net-zero emissions (Levesque *et al* 2021, Rodrigues *et al* 2022).

2.1. Modelling improvements

PRIMES-BuiMo (Capros 2018) is a hybrid economy-engineering model used for the development of scenarios for the residential and services buildings sector of EU member states under alternative policy futures (Fotiou *et al* 2019). Decision-making of agents concerning energy efficiency interventions, including choices about the upgrade of heating equipment, and the timing and depth of renovation, is modelled endogenously based on microeconomic theory, while respecting engineering constraints. The modelling framework represents market (i.e., true costs relating to hidden up-front investments and limited access to capital resources) and non-market (i.e., perceived costs relating to the lack of information, presence of uncertainty and economic factors related to individual consumers) barriers which influence energy efficiency investments. A range of economic (e.g., taxes and subsidies) and regulatory (e.g., minimum energy performance standards) measures to accelerate the energy transition are also modelled (Fotiou *et al* 2022).

PRIMES-BuiMo treats consumer heterogeneity by splitting households into several categories, according to the location, age of construction, income class, and type of household (single or multi-story building). Deviating from the single representative consumer hypothesis, the model portrays agent groups with idiosyncratic behaviours and energy preferences. Subjective discount rates are differentiated by income class to reflect differences in the availability of funding opportunities, access to information and uncertainty. Moreover, PRIMES-BuiMo employs discrete choice theory to capture consumer heterogeneity within household groups. In this way, the model represents heterogeneous consumer decisions, respecting the purchase of energy-related equipment and technologies or improvement of building thermal insulation.

EDGE-Buildings is a simulation model that projects global energy demand for buildings, following a top-down approach driven by population, GDP and climate data projections (Levesque *et al* 2018, Levesque *et al* 2019). Per capita useful energy demand for end uses is projected into the future based on the observed correlation with macro-economic drivers and, in the case of space heating and cooling, influenced by changing climatic conditions. The observed elasticity between the useful energy demand and macro-economic drivers can be altered to represent behavioural or legislative changes. The building shell efficiency is represented by an aggregated thermal transmittance indicator that improves over time. The effect of increased renovation activity is calibrated to pathways with a known renovation rate. As EDGE-Buildings can only simulate scenarios that follow current trends, for transformative scenarios under stringent climate policy, assessments are performed using REMIND-Buildings. REMIND is a global multi-regional IAM which represents the full economy, with a detailed representation of the energy system (Baumstark *et al* 2021). REMIND-Buildings is calibrated to baseline scenarios of final energy demand devised with EDGE-Buildings.

Both the PRIMES and EDGE/REMIND modelling suite treat lifestyle transformations in the residential sector, not relating to energy efficiency measures, via ad-hoc exogenous assumptions. These assumptions are applied to model parameters controlling the activity level for different residential end-uses. More specific details on model characteristics can be found in the Supplementary Information (SI) in section S1.

For this study, both models have undergone enhancements first regarding the breakdown of energy demand to individual residential end-uses, especially for thermal services (i.e. including space and water heating, and space cooling). This is achieved through bottom-up engineering-based functions with an improved distinction between the behavioural and non-behavioural factors driving useful energy demand, that is the amount of energy that should be supplied to final consumers:

- For space heating and cooling, useful energy demand is derived through functions incorporating building-level technical values (e.g., thermal conductivity of building shell/U-value, air infiltration rates), climatic conditions (e.g., heating and cooling degree days—HDDs/CDDs- or the external temperature and length of heating/cooling season), adjusted to include potential behavioural shifts (e.g. changes in internal heating/cooling temperature).
- For water heating, the refined bottom-up functions decompose demand for hot water for personal hygiene purposes to the effect of technical (e.g., showerhead flow rate) and behavioural factors, including the option to reduce the duration of showers.
- In PRIMES-BuiMo, an additional step was taken for calibrating these functions to official energy data from Eurostat (energy balances and split of energy to end uses), thus enabling a more accurate quantification of the effects of behavioural change on useful energy demand.

Second, in order to assess alternative trajectories of floor space growth and their effect on space heating and cooling demand, regional upper limits of floor space growth were set in both models. These caps were defined based on sustainability-focused climate mitigation pathways (Fishman *et al* 2021, Mastrucci *et al* 2021) to reflect policies aiming to limit the expansion of building sizes. Third, the representation of electrical demand for appliances and lighting was improved to better incorporate the effect of behavioural changes. In PRIMES-BuiMo this was achieved by integrating in the scenarios energy saving estimates resulting from the choice of eco-mode over standard washing programmes for dishwashers and laundry machines, and from eliminating standby power from appliances. The impact of these measures was reflected implicitly in the scenarios created by EDGE-Buildings.

2.2. Scenario development

Scenarios developed for the residential buildings sector of EU-27 countries and the UK extend from a historical baseline year common between the models (2015) to 2050, in 5-year intervals. To enhance comparability across scenarios, the sectoral models use harmonised socio-economic assumptions regarding GDP and population growth. Population estimates are based on Eurostat's EUROPOP2019 projections, updated in the short-term to

reflect the influx of refugees from the Ukraine⁴. GDP projections are based on forecasts developed by the Directorate General for Economic and Financial Affairs (DG ECFIN 2021, 2022). The scenario analysis for the residential sector considers two distinct climate targets based on the current EU climate policy landscape. On the one hand, the ‘Baseline’ scenario (existing policy framework) considers only currently implemented climate and energy policies in EU Member States, such as those presented in their National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) and long-term renovation strategies. It follows the general energy, economic and emission trends presented in the latest EU Reference scenario of the European Commission (Capros *et al* 2021).

On the other hand, the ‘Decarbonisation’ scenario assumes much more ambitious EU climate policies in 2030, including the 55% GHG emission reduction target relative to 1990, and stringent energy efficiency and renewable energy targets (as those presented in the Fit for 55 package (EC 2021)). Furthermore, this scenario leads to climate neutrality by 2050 in line with the goals of the EU’s Green Deal (EC 2019). The decarbonisation scenarios assume that various regulatory (e.g. building energy codes, carbon tax) and non-regulatory policies (e.g. subsidies, information and education policies) facilitate the green transition supporting the up-take of clean energy technologies and corresponding investment. However, both the basic Baseline and Decarbonisation policy context overlook the potential energy and emission impacts from more ambitious lifestyle-led demand transitions.

On top of the two climate policy scenarios, three distinct assumptions have been imposed concerning future lifestyle changes: (a) a scenario that assumes no shift in consumer behaviours and a continuation of current trends in energy consumption habits, (b) a Low Ambition lifestyle change scenario variant assuming that a small share of consumers adopts lifestyle changes (gradually until 2050) to reduce their energy consumption and carbon footprint, and (3) a High Ambition lifestyle change scenario variant assuming that a larger share of consumers adopts lifestyle changes of similar or increased intensity compared to the low-ambition case. Combining the two levels of climate policy ambition (‘Baseline’ and ‘Decarbonisation’) with the three levers of lifestyle change (‘No’, ‘Low’ and ‘High’), results in six possible scenario configurations simulated with the two models (labelled as ‘Base’, ‘Base_LC’, ‘Base_LC_High’, ‘Decarb’, ‘Decarb_LC’, and ‘Decarb_LC_High’).

2.2.1. Selection of lifestyle changes

The identification of the most important lifestyle changes to be included in the scenarios for the residential sector is based on the findings of a recent literature review (Andreou *et al* 2022) and other research from the H2020 CAMPAIGNERS project⁵ (Copinschi *et al* 2022, Andreou *et al* 2023). Results from literature reviews helped to identify the demand-side measures with the largest potential in reducing sectoral energy use and carbon emissions. Following the ASI framework (van den Berg *et al* 2021)⁶, the focus was primarily placed on the ‘avoid’ and ‘shift’ type of mitigation actions, rather than on the ‘improve’ ones. These require mainly voluntary actions from consumers, without needing large upfront capital investments. These findings were then complemented with experts’ insights and preliminary empirical information from the CAMPAIGNERS network on the lifestyle changes with the highest adoption probability by consumers.

The final list of lifestyle changes covers actions curtailing energy demand for heating and cooling in buildings, such as shifting the thermostat set-point for heating and cooling, and limiting hot water use for personal hygiene purposes. It also includes developments which lead to reduced floor space in residential buildings. For electrical uses, selected mitigation actions include the choice of eco-mode settings in laundry machines and dishwashers and elimination of standby power from appliances. Finally, we recognised that demand-side actions other than those strictly defined as lifestyle changes can contribute significantly to decarbonisation goals (Ivanova *et al* 2020). As a result, the LC variants also examine the effect of accelerating building renovation on decarbonisation goals; an action also included in the NAVIGATE study (Kriegler *et al* 2023).

2.2.2. Quantification of lifestyle changes

Scenario assumptions concerning lifestyle changes in the residential sector were translated into a compatible input to the modelling framework of PRIMES-BuiMo and EDGE-Buildings. The quantification of lifestyle changes draws from the results of a literature review performed for the H2020 CAMPAIGNERS (Andreou *et al* 2023) and NAVIGATE⁷ projects and input from the H2020 MutliFutures⁸ and PRISMA⁹ (Pettifor *et al* 2024)

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/PROJ_STP22/default/table?lang=en&category=proj.proj_19n

⁵ <https://www.climate-campaigners.com/>

⁶ Avoid actions involve a reduction in the overall level of an energy service, while shift ones require a transition to a more environmental-friendly behaviour. Improve actions mainly consist of opting for more efficient technological options.

⁷ <https://www.navigate-h2020.eu/>

⁸ <https://multifutures.eu/>

⁹ <https://www.net0prisma.eu/>

projects. A cross-check assured that lifestyle change assumptions do not deviate significantly with those from similar modelling studies, like those in van den Berg *et al* (2024). The following changes were imposed to the models:

- (a) Set-point temperatures for heating (cooling) in residential buildings reduce (increase) by 1 °C and 2 °C from their baseline levels until 2050 in the Low and High Ambition scenarios respectively. In PRIMES-BuiMo, baseline country-specific internal temperatures were derived from the EN ISO 13790:2008 calculation method for heating and cooling demand (Loga and Diefenbach 2013). In EDGE-Buildings, thermostat setpoints are accounted for in the calculation of degree days which is a driver of heating and cooling demand in the model. Baseline setpoints correspond to HDDs and CDDs calculated with an external balance temperature of 18 °C and 23 °C respectively also considering internal gains and heterogeneity in behaviour and comfort perception (Levesque *et al* 2018).
- (b) The renovation rate in buildings increases by 0.5%pt and 1%pt per year above the Baseline (or the basic Decarbonisation scenario) levels in the Low and High Ambition lifestyle change scenarios respectively. More frequent and deep renovation measures are adopted progressively over time, meaning that the maximum deviation from the basic scenarios is achieved in 2050. Based on PRIMES-BuiMo projections, the average renovation rate in 2050 remains low at around 1%/yr in the Baseline scenario, while more than doubles in the Decarbonisation case reaching 2%/yr. In EDGE-Buildings, the pace of improvement of the U-value is adjusted to reflect a 1%/yr in the baseline case, while it increases to 1.5%/yr and 2%/yr in the Low and High Ambition lifestyle change scenario variants respectively.
- (c) Flexible use of buildings, shared building spaces (e.g. co-housing and co-working) and policies limiting floor space in new constructions reduce the floor space used per capita in the residential sector. We assume a convergence to 30 (High Ambition) and 40 (Low Ambition) m²/cap by 2050 for residential floor space (in line with LED/SSP1 scenario assumptions in Grubler *et al* (2018), Fishman *et al* (2021) and Mastrucci *et al* (2021)). In EDGE-Buildings regions that currently have a higher floor space per capita than the assumed cap maintain this level over time. In the Baseline and Decarbonisation scenarios without lifestyle change, the two models show a convergence of household space to 47–48 m²/cap in 2050 in the EU-27.
- (d) Hot water conservation: In PRIMES-BuiMo, average shower time is decreased down to 5 min in the Low Ambition scenario and down to 4 min in the High ambition scenario, similar to the Low and Very Low demand scenarios presented in Levesque *et al* (2019). This lifestyle change was simulated compared to a baseline showering time of 5.6 min, reported for UK households in Shahmohammadi *et al* (2019). In EDGE-Buildings, reduced shower times from 8 min to 6 min in the Low Ambition scenario and 4 min in the High Ambition scenario are assumed in the bottom-up calculation of water heating demand saturation level. The different target shower time in the low-ambition lifestyle change case reflects the higher baseline showering time relative to PRIMES-BuiMo.
- (e) Choice of eco-mode for clothes and dish washing programmes: Based on data from the European Product Registry for Energy Labelling (EC 2022), the average eco-mode consumption of dishwashers in the market (C to G class) is around 0.85 kWh cycle⁻¹ and that of laundry machines is 0.68 kWh cycle⁻¹. By ignoring class A to B, we isolate the effect of eco-mode without considering the best-performing products in the market. In PRIMES-BuiMo, electricity demand for dishwashers and laundry machines is adjusted according to the reduction in average cycle consumption between eco-mode and standard programmes using as baseline consumption levels those of ‘ordinary’ technologies included in the model¹⁰. In the Low Ambition Lifestyle Change scenario, 50% of households are assumed to choose eco-mode programmes by 2050, while this percentage increases to 100% in the high-ambition case.
- (f) Eliminating standby electricity use: Annual energy savings are estimated based on a review of standby electricity consumption statistics for different product categories (LBNL no date). In PRIMES-BuiMo, standby power estimates were transformed into avoided annual electricity consumption figures based on simplistic assumptions about the daily hours of standby of electric appliances and lighting. In the Low and High Ambition lifestyle change scenario, we assume that 50% and 100% of the households eliminate standby power by 2050 respectively. EDGE-Buildings represents all appliances and lighting as a single category and does not resolve their energy demand any further. The impact of lifestyle changes (e) and (f) is therefore implicitly reflected in the model as the less active use of appliances through a reduction of the elasticity between GDP per capita and the electricity demand of appliances and lighting overall.

¹⁰ PRIMES-Builmo categorises appliances based on their efficiency as ordinary, improved, advanced and future, where learning by doing factors apply on technological development.

Figure 1. Projections of useful energy demand for thermal uses in the scenarios modelled via PRIMES-BuiMo and EDGE-Buildings.

Table 1. Lifestyle change scenario assumptions for the low and high-ambition variant.

Modelled lifestyle change	Low-ambition variant ^a	High-ambition variant ^a
Set-point temperature	1 °C reduction in thermostat setting	2 °C reduction in thermostat setting
Limiting floor space growth	Convergence to 40 m ² /cap	Convergence to 30 m ² /cap
Hot water conservation	Shower time set at 5 or 6 min	Shower time set at 4 min
Eco-mode consumption	50% of households switch to eco-mode for clothes and dishwashing programmes	100% of households switch to eco-mode for clothes and dishwashing programmes
Standby electricity use (appliances and lighting)	50% of households eliminate standby power	100% of households eliminate standby power
Renovation rates	0.5% p.a. increase above the Baseline/Decarbonisation scenario	1% p.a. increase above the Baseline/Decarbonisation scenario

^a Assumptions refer to changes from the levels of scenarios without lifestyle changes in 2050.

Table 1 summarises the key assumptions regarding the lifestyle changes in the residential sector under the low and high-ambition scenario variant. For the high-ambition decarbonisation case, additional variants were created integrating individual lifestyle changes from table 1. These variants incorporate changes in (a) set-point temperature selection, (b) dwelling downsizing, (c) hot water conservation, (d) more efficient appliance use, and (e) increased renovation measures. This helps to decompose total energy savings achieved in the high-ambition LC case (Decarb_LC_High) relative to the basic Decarb scenario to the effect of individual measures.

3. Model-based results

3.1. Useful energy demand

Useful energy demand for residential thermal uses in the EU-27 & UK region increases slightly over time in the Baseline case, as shown in figure 1. This is driven mainly by the growing floor space (see SI/section S2 for energy service level projections), while improvements in the thermal properties of building envelopes have a more limited effect. Integration of lifestyle changes leads to significant reductions in useful energy demand relative to the Baseline case, with the effect reaching a maximum level in 2050 when more households adopt energy-saving lifestyles. Relative to the Baseline case, useful energy demand in 2050 is projected to decline by 17% in the Low Ambition (Base_LC) and 29–34% in the High Ambition (Base_LC_High) scenario, with the two models showing similar trends. Due to its magnitude, the largest contributor to the projected decrease is space heating (which is reduced via thermostat set-point adjustments, declining floor space and increased renovation), with a 80–90% contribution share (see SI/section S2 for detailed figures)¹¹.

¹¹ Detailed model outputs can also be found in Andreou et al (2024).

Figure 2. Change of EU-27&UK residential final energy use in 2030 and 2050 in the modelled scenarios, relative to 2015 levels.

In the decarbonisation scenarios family generated with PRIMES-BuiMo, useful energy demand in 2050 is reduced by 13–42% relative to the Baseline case, similarly driven by the declining space heating needs. The scenario achieving the strongest reduction in useful energy demand is as expected the Decarb_LC_High, which assumes high annual renovation rates and depth, and the most intense lifestyle changes combined with ambitious policies towards net-zero emissions. Decarbonisation scenarios from REMIND are not shown as the model does not report end-uses at sufficient granularity.

3.2. Final energy

Based on models' projections, final energy use in the residential sector of the EU-27&UK region in the Baseline case changes from 12 EJ yr⁻¹ in 2015 to 10–12 EJ yr⁻¹ in 2030 and decreases to 9 EJ yr⁻¹ in 2050, representing a ~20% reduction from current levels (see SI/section S2 for a breakdown to fuel and end-use shares). PRIMES-BuiMo shows that stronger energy savings are realised earlier compared to REMIND-Buildings. This is the result of ambitious energy efficiency and renewable energy policy targets in 2030 explicitly represented in the modelling framework of PRIMES. REMIND-Buildings on the other hand projects higher mid-term baseline demand. There is however good agreement of the relative reduction from LC between the models, as shown in figure 2.

The impact of lifestyle changes on energy consumption in the baseline scenarios is significant, especially in the long-term: in the low and high-ambition LC cases, residential energy use is respectively shown to decrease by 15–16% and 27–30% in 2050 relative to the Base scenario with no lifestyle change. The two models also agree about the relative decrease in final energy by 2050 under the decarbonisation scenario, projecting a 25–26% reduction with respect to baseline levels. Furthermore, the energy savings from behavioural shifts in the decarbonisation context are slightly smaller compared to baseline scenarios, as the reduction in final energy in 2050 relative to the basic Decarb case is only 14% and 26–27%, respectively for the low and high-ambition scenario variant.

Moreover, the two models agree about the additional benefits from raising the ambition level of lifestyle changes in the residential sector from 'low' to 'high'. In the current policy context, more widespread adoption of low-carbon behaviours increases the energy savings by 12–14 p.p. in 2050; while the corresponding savings in the decarbonisation context are relatively smaller at 9–10 p.p., showing the diminishing returns from an increased shift to low-carbon behaviours in a progressively decarbonised system.

3.3. CO₂ emissions

Baseline CO₂ emissions in the EU-27&UK residential sector (figure 3), are projected to decrease in PRIMES-BuiMo by 25% and 51% in 2030 and 2050 respectively, relative to 2015 levels. Conversely, REMIND-Buildings projects a somewhat lower decrease in Base scenario emissions, which amounts to 18% in 2030 and 44% in 2050 below 2015 levels. The less pronounced reduction in baseline emissions in 2030 can be explained by the smaller change in total energy demand from current levels; while in 2050 this can be traced back to the higher share of remaining coal and liquids compared to the final energy demand of PRIMES.

Similarly in the decarbonisation scenario, PRIMES-BuiMo projects CO₂ emissions from households to reduce in 2030 by 52%, while the corresponding reduction in REMIND-Buildings is lower at 36%. Nevertheless, emissions in both models virtually reach zero by 2050, as strong decarbonisation policies drive the significant electrification of the sector and massive displacement of fossil fuels combined with the uptake of zero-carbon options, such as heat pumps and district heating.

Emission reductions increase in the lifestyle change variants with emissions in the low(high)-ambition LC baseline scenario dropping further by 4 p.p. (10 p.p.) in 2030 and 7–8 p.p. (16–17 p.p.) in 2050 compared to the core baseline case. In agreement with final energy demand results, the impact of lifestyle change on emissions is less significant in a decarbonisation setting, as the maximum additional emission reduction in the two models is 6 p.p. in 2030 and almost negligible by 2050 as net zero emissions are already achieved in the region. CO₂ emissions in both models display greater variation between the core decarbonisation and baseline case, compared to the variation observed between the core scenario and its lifestyle change variants.

3.4. Costs

This section compares the costs incurred by consumers in the residential sector under the various scenarios, based on PRIMES-BuiMo results (figure 4). The cost indicators selected are annual fuel expenses and capital costs, which comprises payments for direct energy efficiency measures (renovation and new building constructions) and for new energy equipment (e.g. heating equipment, electric and electronic appliances etc).

Fuel purchasing expenses reduce in the decarbonisation scenario relative to the baseline, around 1% when cumulated over the period 2021–2050. Factors like the introduction of carbon price in non-ETS sectors from 2030 onwards which increases fossil fuel prices, mitigate the reduction in fuel expenses due to lower energy demand. Lifestyle changes reduce even more the cumulative fuel expenses over the period 2021–2050 by 6–7% and 13–14% in the low- and high-ambition LC scenarios respectively, compared to the Base and Decarb scenarios without lifestyle changes. In this way, lifestyle changes are effective in reducing energy expenditure¹².

Compared to the baseline case, capital costs in the decarbonisation scenario increase by about 20% over the 2021–2050 period. This is influenced by policies enabling additional capital investments in energy efficiency, based on a higher rate and depth of buildings' renovation and the accelerated uptake of capital-intensive low-carbon technologies, including heat pumps, as well as energy efficient equipment and appliances. As a result, capital costs in 2050 for the Base and Decarb case are respectively 80% and 120% higher than the corresponding 2020 level.

In the lifestyle change variants, changes in capital costs are driven by two opposite effects, namely the increased spending on renovation measures assumed in the LC variants counterbalanced by the reduced investments in energy-using equipment as thermal needs are lower (lower household space, lower temperature set-point). As the latter is a larger cost element, cumulative capital costs under the LC variants are lower than the cases without lifestyle changes both in the baseline and decarbonisation context. Over the 2021–2050 period,

¹² In this study reduced fuel expenses are only the result of lower energy demand due to lifestyle changes in the residential sector. Potential secondary impacts on end-use fuel prices or private consumption of households from declining energy demand are not considered here, as this would require the use of full energy-system and economy-wide modelling tools.

Figure 4. Annual fuel expenses and costs for capital based on PRIMES-BuiMo results.

capital costs reduce in the LC (LC_High) case by 1% (3%) in the baseline, and 1% (4%) in the decarbonisation scenario, relative to the no lifestyle change cases. Cumulative total energy-related costs (comprising capital costs and energy purchases) are therefore reduced by 4% and 8% under the low and high-ambition lifestyle change case respectively, for both the baseline and decarbonisation scenario. The share of cumulative operating to total costs drops from 49% in the baseline scenario to 41% in the Decarb_LC_High case while the share of capital costs increases due to the investment in buildings' renovation and the purchase of more capital-intensive (and energy efficient) technologies and appliances.

3.5. Decomposition analysis

This section elaborates on the results of the decomposition analysis of energy savings achieved in the decarbonisation scenarios incorporating individual high-ambition behavioural changes compared to the Decarb case without lifestyle changes. Amongst the assessed measures/lifestyle changes, the one having the strongest impact on final energy use for both PRIMES and REMIND is the reduction of average household space, with cumulative savings of 12–14 EJ in the 2021–2050 period relative to the Decarb case (figure 5). The second most effective measure is thermostat set-point adjustments according to PRIMES, with cumulative energy savings of around 7 EJ. Conversely in REMIND, increased renovation has the second largest effect (11 EJ savings), followed by thermostat adjustments (8 EJ savings).

In PRIMES, intensification of renovation measures has a much less pronounced contribution to overall energy savings, as in the basic Decarb scenario the modelled energy efficiency policies already lead to an increased rate and depth of renovation leaving a smaller room for further energy demand reductions in the LC cases. The decreasing effect on useful energy demand via increased building renovation under the basic Decarb case is represented more coarsely in REMIND such that the effect of an additional increase of the renovation rate has to be calibrated to results from models including explicit renovation activity. Appliance use has a moderate impact on energy savings in both models (~6EJ savings), while hot water conservation measures has the lowest impact (~3EJ savings).

Adding together the energy savings resulting from individual behavioural measures leads to a level of total savings that is higher than the ones achieved under the Decarb_LC_High scenario (plotted in figure 5). This could be explained by the potential (but moderate) trade-offs between lifestyle changes targeting demand for space heating and cooling, namely the interplay between building renovation choices and exogenous assumptions about changing thermostat temperature set-points and dwelling size. In the scenarios where renovation rates are unconstrained, the introduction of individual exogenous measures on top of the Decarb scenario leads to energy savings according to the mitigation potential (in % terms) of each action. Enforcing higher renovation rates and depth in the Decarb_LC_High case results in a lower useful energy demand for space heating relative to the Decarb case, thereby limiting the room for additional savings from other behavioural measures.

4. Discussion

4.1. Impact of lifestyle changes and policy implications

The critical role of behavioural shifts in shaping future energy consumption patterns in the residential sector is emphasised in both models' results, especially in the long-term when the uptake of lifestyle changes is maximised. This is particularly evident under the baseline scenario's specifications where lifestyle shifts result in substantial reductions in energy demand and CO₂ emissions from the residential sector. This showcases the significant contribution of radical demand-side transitions and lifestyle changes in achieving energy efficiency and CO₂ reduction goals.

Savings from lifestyle changes in the baseline context for the low-ambition scenario variant are broadly consistent but on the high end of the range of estimates from previous similar studies. EU-level residential emissions in the Low Ambition scenario decrease by 18–20% from their baseline level in 2050, which compares well with the 16% and 12% emissions reduction estimates in the global and European lifestyle case of van Sluisveld *et al* (2016) and Costa *et al* (2021)¹³ respectively. The impact on CO₂ emissions in 2050 is somewhat larger compared to the 9% reduction estimate derived from the 'Pocket Lifestyles' scenario in van den Berg *et al* (2024). The smaller impact can be explained by the lower saturation rate of various lifestyle changes in 2050 compared to the 100% rate adopted in our study and the non inclusion of building renovation in the list of behavioural measures. Furthermore, comparison with previous studies demonstrates the optimistic nature of our High Ambition lifestyle change case, which requires a radical up-scaling of behaviours and social norms in the residential sector. In the baseline high-ambition scenario variant, our models project CO₂ emissions to reduce by 61–68% between 2015 and 2050. This is still within the 40–70% range of the technical potential for emissions reduction in 2050 through demand-side actions in all end-use sectors, as estimated by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (Creutzig *et al* 2022b).

Lifestyle change impacts on energy efficiency and decarbonisation goals are smaller under a climate-neutrality policy framework (in agreement with van Sluisveld *et al* (2016)). This suggests that the effectiveness of lifestyle changes depends also on broader climate action. While most of the emission reduction effort is attributed to the overall decarbonisation measures, lifestyle changes could still have a complementary role and support medium-term goals in case of weaker implementation of decarbonisation policies. Results suggest that lifestyle changes, such as reducing average dwelling size and thermostat set-point adjustments, can act as a substantial complementary driver to climate policies in a decarbonisation setting to accelerate the EU's transition.

Moving to economic considerations, scenario results highlight that lifestyle changes can lower energy expenditure for residential consumers as they lead to reduced fuel expenses, irrespective of the policy context. Moreover, under the decarbonisation context where ambitious policies drive additional investments in energy efficiency, lifestyle changes can be effective in mitigating the increases in capital expenditure incurred by consumers. Overall, this provides evidence that the role of lifestyle changes in the policy agenda could be

¹³ This estimate covers all GHG emissions instead.

two-fold, one for the contribution to decarbonisation goals and another for reducing energy costs for consumers. Lower expenditures due to lifestyle changes could potentially aid in the reduction of the risk of energy poverty for low-income European households, and support broader SDGs with clear co-benefits in terms of reduced air pollution, improved health and enhanced sustainability.

The overall findings of this study underline the need for designing mitigation strategies tailored to the residential sector's challenges and potentials, with a strong representation of radical demand-side transitions and lifestyle changes. However, caution is needed in the promotion of lifestyle changes to the extent to which they do not compromise well-being and hinder progress towards achieving decent living standards (Millward-Hopkins *et al* 2020). Currently, these elements lack significant representation in most of the current EU-wide policies and national climate strategies (Salem *et al* 2021). Some exceptions exist for EU countries, such as in the long-term strategies of Austria and Portugal (Federal Ministry Republic of Austria 2019, Republica Portuguesa 2019), which incorporate some behavioural changes for buildings, however mostly focusing on building renovation measures.

4.2. Limitations and future work

The robust integration of diverse lifestyle changes and behavioural shifts into leading IAMs and ESMs, an aspect which is often overlooked in traditional modelling approaches, allows for a better understanding of their potential contribution to a low-carbon transition. This study has focused on modelling lifestyle changes and their impacts on the EU-27&UK residential sector, through improving two leading sectoral energy models. The performed analysis informs policy makers about the potential contribution and added value of environmentally sustainable lifestyle changes of increased intensity and adoptability for the net-zero transition goals.

Despite the rich representation of lifestyle change impacts in the modelled scenarios, our approach has some limitations. First, with the exception of building renovation in PRIMES-BuiMo, lifestyle changes are represented in our models in an exogenous manner; a common feature of ESM/IAM-based approaches (Andreou *et al* 2022, Krumm *et al* 2022). As a result, a comprehensive analysis of the implementation barriers, enabling factors and policy costs incurred by lifestyle transitions was not performed. Second, due to the unavailability of information on heterogeneous energy preferences, the scenarios have applied a uniform change in lifestyles across household groups. Not comprehensively representing actor heterogeneity does not allow studying the varying responses of consumer types to policies targeting lifestyle changes (Keppo *et al* 2021). Third, despite our effort to validate our scenario assumptions about lifestyle changes through reviews and expert insights, the real extent to which such demand-side transitions can happen has remained outside the scope of this study.

Future work could focus in endogenising lifestyles in large-scale IAM/ESM models and representing the heterogeneity of energy preferences between diverse consumer groups. For buildings, research could focus on the drivers and more importantly the psychological and infrastructural barriers of behavioural shifts with a high mitigation potential, such as reducing average living space size (Huebner and Shipworth 2017) or changing the thermostat set-point. A promising approach is the linking of IAMs/ESMs with tools grounded on rich empirical data on energy use behaviours, such as statistical lifestyle modules (Pettifor *et al* 2024) and agent-based models (Niamir *et al* 2020, Niamir *et al* 2024). A linkage with an agent-based model can in particular aid in capturing complex social dynamics, such as lifestyle changes, as they have rich representation of heterogeneous actor characteristics and can simulate social interaction and learning effectively.

Moreover, the scope could be broadened to include other domains with a large carbon footprint and high sensitivity to behavioural change such as mobility, diet and consumer goods (Grubler *et al* 2018, Ivanova *et al* 2020). Systemic analysis -using full-system IAMs- can also provide a more holistic representation of lifestyle change impacts on the energy system, including energy supply, but also in land-uses and in the broader economy and society. Testing the generalisation of findings could involve expanding the geographical scope to encompass other regions, including other developed or less-developed economies (van den Berg *et al* 2021).

5. Conclusions

Achieving the ambitious decarbonisation targets set by the PA requires significant efforts on the supply and demand side of energy-economy systems. Unlike supply-side solutions, demand-side actions have not been explored extensively in ESM- and IAM-based studies, thus less is known about the drivers, impacts and mitigation potential of lifestyle changes in end-use sectors. This study aims to improve the representation of behavioural change in the mathematical framework of two sectoral models for buildings (PRIMES-BuiMo and EDGE-Buildings), by focusing on a more accurate split of residential energy demand to specific end-uses and disaggregation of the behavioural and non-behavioural factors driving useful energy demand. The improved sectoral models are used to devise scenarios for the evolution of energy use, CO₂ emissions and consumer expenditure in the European residential sector, under varying assumptions about the strength of climate policy

targets and the adoption of lifestyle changes. The multi-model analysis of lifestyle change impacts showcases the level of uncertainty governing the development of low energy demand pathways and the need for employing diverse modelling tools to perform similar assessments capturing a range of the associated uncertainty.

Our study, building on improved methodologies in sectoral models, demonstrates the important role of lifestyle changes as a potential complementary driver to climate policies for achieving low-carbon transitions, by contributing not only to additional energy and CO₂ savings but also to important cost reductions for residential consumers. This highlights that policies need to incorporate characteristics of low energy demand transitions, while addressing the drivers, costs, and barriers of ambitious lifestyle changes. Future work could focus on internalising some of these elements in the modelling frameworks of ESMs and IAMs.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13711481>.

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